

IRON DEFICIENCY DURING PREGNANCY

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Abstract

This article provides information about iron deficiency during pregnancy, republican medical institutions, maternity complexes, the special condition of the female body, and the health care system of the Republic of Uzbekistan in modern conditions.

Key words

obstetric, gynecological, perinatal, reproductive, fertile, zygote, iron.

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada xomiladorlik davrida temir moddasining yetishmasligi, respublika tibbiyot muassasalari, tug'ruq komplekslari, ayol organizmining maxsus holati, zamonaviy sharoitda O'zbekiston Respublikasi sog'liqni saqlash tizimi haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar

akusherlik, ginekologik, perinatal, reproduktiv, fertil, zigota, temir moddasi.

Аннотация

В данной статье представлена информация о дефиците железа при беременности, республиканских медицинских учреждениях, родильных комплексах, особом состоянии женского организма, системе здравоохранения Республики Узбекистан в современных условиях.

Ключевые Слова

акушерский, гинекологический, перинатальный, репродуктивный, фертильный, зигота, железа.

INTRODUCTION.

Protection of motherhood and childhood, development of obstetrics and gynecological care, reduction of maternal, perinatal and infant diseases and death are important directions of the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan in modern conditions. Nursing professionals have a clear potential to meet the needs of women in effective healthcare. "National model" of protection of maternal and

child health is important for the restoration and maintenance of reproductive health of the female part of the population.

For republican medical institutions such as perinatal centers, it is important to strengthen the material and technical base of maternity complexes, organize medical examinations of women of childbearing age, and positively solve the issues related to monitoring the health of mothers and children during pregnancy and childbirth.

REFERENCES AND METHODOLOGY.

The achievements made within the healthcare system in Uzbekistan have been recognized by famous international organizations. Therefore, in the report of the international organization "Save the Children", prepared by the researchers of this organization, special attention was paid to the achievements of Uzbekistan in protecting motherhood and childhood. According to the report, it was noted that our country ranks 19th among 125 countries of the world in terms of creating conditions for women.

Pregnancy (lat. *graviditas* .) is a special condition of a woman's body, which is the presence of a developing embryo or fetus in her reproductive organs. Pregnancy occurs as a result of the union of female and male germ cells in the fallopian tube, resulting in the formation of **a zygote** containing 46 chromosomes

Anemia is the result of a decrease in the level of hemoglobin and the number of erythrocytes in the blood. Anemia in pregnancy occurs as a result of increased consumption of iron by the fetus. If it is insufficiently replenished due to unstable nutrition of a pregnant woman. And as the baby grows, iron consumption increases. Thus, if a woman spends about two or three milligrams in the first trimester of the amount consumed before pregnancy, in the second trimester this figure increases to three or four milligrams per day. In the third trimester, a woman should replenish at least ten to twelve milligrams of iron per day. Thus, iron deficiency during pregnancy is mainly detected at the last stage.

RESULTS AND METHODOLOGY.

Causes of anemia during pregnancy

Along with increased iron intake from the developing fetus, there are also factors that cause iron deficiency anemia. Among them:

- multiple pregnancies;
- early (under 17) or late (after 37) pregnancy;
- bleeding during pregnancy;
- taking unknown drugs (to neutralize acid);

- previous surgery on the intestine and stomach, because iron in its composition is not broken down from food;
- poor nutrition, anorexia;
- Re-pregnancy within 3 years;
- chronic diseases - hepatitis, pyelonephritis, stomach ulcer, heart disease.

Symptoms of anemia during pregnancy

Lack of iron in a woman's body is manifested by weakness and frequent relapses, rapid fatigue, rapid heart rate, shortness of breath with physical exertion.

However, these symptoms are observed even with 2nd degree anemia or severe anemia. And a pregnant woman cannot feel special. Determining the onset of the disease can only be done by conducting a blood test.

Severity levels of anemia:

1. **Easy:** his hemoglobin level is 110-90 g/l.
2. **Average:** the amount of hemoglobin decreases to 90-70 g / l.
3. **Serious:** hemoglobin level is below 70 g/l.

Thus, the norm of iron during pregnancy is 120-130 g / l.

Prevention of anemia in pregnant women

First, it is a complete food that contains protein and iron content. Meat and dairy products, fruits (apples, pomegranates) and vegetables (cabbage, turnips, carrots) are especially useful. If there are cases of preventing anemia in women with a high risk of developing the disease, the doctor prescribes iron preparations in the form of tablets or pills.

What are the risks of anemia in pregnancy?

The threat of iron deficiency during pregnancy - iron deficiency anemia develops bad dystrophic processes in the placenta and uterus. They lead to placental disorders and the formation of placental insufficiency as a result. Anemia is dangerous for the baby, it causes him to lose enough nutrients and oxygen, which leads to a delay in his development.

Iron overload anemia during pregnancy is even more dangerous. In this case, normalizing the level of iron is more difficult than its deficiency. This is due to the storage of "excess" iron in the liver, heart or pancreas. This condition is called hemochromatosis. Iron poisoning is manifested by diarrhea, vomiting, inflammation of the kidneys, paralysis of the central nervous system.

Excess iron in the body can occur as a result of various blood diseases or long-term consumption of iron. Iron accumulates in tissues and organs, which negatively affects the functioning of the body. Excess glands in pregnant women

lead to placental pathology. Therefore, the consumption of iron during pregnancy, its doses and the duration of the course should be strictly determined by the doctor.

BLOOD-PRODUCING PRODUCTS

- Beef liver is a very good product for increasing hemoglobin in the blood. Special attention should be paid to its quality. You can boil beef liver, add boiled carrots and onions, grind it in a blender and make pate.

- Boiled tongue also cures anemia well, it is necessary to eat at least 50 grams per day.

- There is a famous mixture to increase blood and immunity. This mixture consists of nuts, dried fruits, honey and lemon. Raisins, sorrel, walnuts, honey and one lemon are often taken from 200 grams. Ingredients are passed through a meat grinder, then honey is added. One tablespoon is consumed 3 times a day.

- It is recommended to include citrus fruits in the diet, because the vitamin C contained in them helps the absorption of iron. Fruits containing vitamin C: *lemon, pomegranate, orange, kiwi, strawberry, grapefruit*. In addition, to quickly increase hemoglobin in the blood, you can drink freshly squeezed juices: pomegranate, carrot, beet juice. About 5% of iron is absorbed from fruits and vegetables.

According to research, products have been announced that help increase the amount of hemoglobin in the blood. Accordingly, leguminous products also increase the amount of hemoglobin. These are different varieties of peas, lentils (*chechevitsa*), beans, which contain a large amount of iron.

Doctors recommend people with low hemoglobin to eat oily fish.

In this regard, beets are leading among vegetables. Watermelon, melon, tomatoes, peaches, pomegranates and black currants are also useful.

Eating buckwheat, barley groats, buckwheat, nuts and pistachios is good for increasing hemoglobin.

Another blood-enhancing product is bilberry. It will be necessary to prepare a tincture. A liter of boiling water is poured into a handful of namatak fruits and left overnight in a thermos. In the morning, the tincture is filtered and honey is added to taste. This drink is equally useful for children and adults. Drink half a glass of this tincture several times a day before meals.

CONCLUSION

To ensure a therapeutic effect, that is, to increase the level of iron in the blood, a person should regularly consume these products in sufficient quantities. Clinically, supplementing the diet with iron-rich foods may be recommended in

addition to taking medications. But in order to prevent iron deficiency and, as a rule, to maintain a healthy lifestyle, a different diet is definitely recommended.

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